

CLINICAL PHARMACIST INSIGHTS INTO POSTPARTUM HYPERTENSION FOLLOWING LSCS: UNMASKING PHARMACOLOGICAL TRIGGERS AND CLINICAL COMPLEXITIES

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ABSTRACT:

Postpartum hypertension is a clinically significant complication that may arise following lower segment caesarean section (LSCS), often triggered by pharmacological agents such as NSAIDs or abrupt cessation of magnesium sulfate, as well as fluid overload. This case report presents a series of postpartum women who developed new-onset or persistent hypertension following LSCS, highlighting the role of pharmacological contributors. A key focus is placed on the involvement of the clinical pharmacist in identifying drug-induced hypertensive triggers, assessing fluid administration practices, and guiding antihypertensive therapy. Through active participation in medication review and interdisciplinary collaboration, the clinical pharmacist contributed to timely interventions that improved patient outcomes and prevented further complications. This case underscores the importance of integrating clinical pharmacy services in obstetric care to enhance patient safety and therapeutic efficacy.

Keywords: Postpartum hypertension, case series, clinical pharmacist

INTRODUCTION:

Postpartum hypertension is a clinically significant condition that can emerge in women who previously had normal blood pressure or as a continuation of gestational hypertension and preeclampsia^[1,2]. Following lower segment caesarean section (LSCS), hypertension can manifest due to multiple factors, including fluid overload, pharmacological triggers,

and underlying preeclampsia^[3]. The recognition and management of postpartum hypertension are crucial to prevent complications such as eclampsia, stroke, and hypertensive crises^[4].

In modern interdisciplinary care, clinical pharmacists have emerged as vital team members, particularly in identifying drug-related triggers and optimizing therapeutic strategies. Their role in medication review, fluid balance assessment, and monitoring for adverse drug reactions is crucial in preventing complications such as eclampsia, stroke, and hypertensive crises.

This case series presents five instances of postpartum hypertension following LSCS, exploring potential etiologies, including pharmacological influences (e.g., NSAIDs like diclofenac), excessive fluid administration, and the natural hemodynamic shifts of the postpartum period.

ILLUSTRATIVE CASES

Case 1: Development of Postpartum Hypertension in a woman with Intrauterine Growth Restriction (IUGR)

Mrs. Neha, a 20-year-old primigravida, admitted at 37 weeks + 5 days of gestation with complaints of reduced Fetal growth and other associated concerns. She was diagnosed with intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR) and monitored closely for maternal and Fetal well-being.

Clinical Course:

She had complaints of perceiving Fetal movements and a three-day history of cough, for which a chest X-ray and obstetrician evaluation were advised. Clinical assessment revealed the presence of intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR) with adequate amniotic fluid levels and a posteriorly located placenta with Grade II maturity.

Her antenatal history was unremarkable, with no history of major illnesses such as hypertension, diabetes, or thyroid dysfunction. There was also no history of epilepsy or blood transfusions. During her antenatal care, she was given routine folic acid supplementation, tetanus toxoid injections, and two doses of Inj. Betamethasone to

promote fetal lung maturity in anticipation of possible preterm delivery. Physical examination showed no abnormalities, and systemic examinations of her cardiovascular and respiratory systems were normal. The abdominal examination confirmed a cephalic presentation with good fetal movements.

Upon admission, her vitals were stable, but considering the risk of preeclampsia, Inj. Magnesium Sulphate ($MgSO_4$) was administered. A loading dose of 4 g was given via slow IV infusion over 20 minutes to prevent and manage potential eclamptic seizures, which are a significant complication of severe preeclampsia. This intervention was followed by close monitoring of her neurological status and vital signs.

Due to concerns about fetal well-being, Mrs. Neha was closely observed until spontaneous vaginal delivery (SVD) occurred on 27/12/2024 at 7:32 AM. She delivered a healthy male baby weighing 2735 g, who cried immediately after birth, indicating good neonatal health.

Treatment Given:

1. **Inj. Betamethasone:** Two doses administered to enhance fetal lung maturity in anticipation of potential preterm delivery.
2. **Inj. Magnesium Sulphate ($MgSO_4$):** Loading dose of 4 g IV given over 20 minutes to prevent eclamptic seizures in the context of preeclampsia risk.
3. **Jonac Suppository (Diclofenac):** Cumulative dose of 600 mg post-delivery for pain relief.
4. **IV Fluids:**
 - Day 1: 2200 mL of Ringer's Lactate (RL).
 - Day 2: 1500 mL of Ringer's Lactate+ Normal Saline (RL+NS).
 - Day 3: 500ml of Normal Saline
 - Day 4: 500ml of Normal Saline

Postpartum Course:**Monitoring and Observations:**

Post-delivery, Mrs. Neha was monitored for vital signs, including blood pressure. A transient rise in BP was noted postpartum, potentially linked to:

1. **Drug-Induced Effects:** Jonac suppository (diclofenac) is known to cause transient hypertension in certain patients.
2. **Fluid Overload:** The cumulative administration of 4700 mL of IV fluids over two days could have contributed to fluid retention and subsequent BP changes.

Case 2: Development of Postpartum Hypertension in a Woman with No Prior History of Hypertension

Patient Details: Mrs. Pooja, a 30-year-old female (Gravida 2 Para 1), was admitted on 16/10/2024 and underwent an emergency lower segment caesarean section (LSCS) on 17/10/2024 due to fetal distress. She delivered a live male baby weighing 2.75 kg. Her blood group is A-positive, and she was discharged on 23/10/2024.

Obstetric History: The patient's current pregnancy was spontaneous, and she was regularly immunized and booked. Anomaly and growth scans were normal, with findings of cephalic presentation and posterior placenta. Amniotic fluid index (AFI) was 10 cm, and the estimated fetal weight was 1.55 kg. She has a history of one spontaneous abortion in 2023 at 7 weeks, for which medical management was done.

Medical History: The patient has no known history of hypertension, diabetes, thyroid dysfunction, or epilepsy. However, she received six doses of intravenous iron for anaemia during this pregnancy and showed no allergic reactions. There is no history of blood transfusion.

Clinical Course: Mrs. Pooja was admitted with complaints of abdominal pain and reduced fetal movements. After evaluation, emergency LSCS was performed under spinal anaesthesia. The immediate intraoperative and postoperative periods were uneventful.

Postpartum Complications: By postpartum day 2, the patient developed elevated blood pressure readings (ranging between 140/90 mmHg and 160/100 mmHg), raising concern for postpartum hypertension. She also reported symptoms of headache, and mild pedal edema

was noted. Laboratory investigations revealed normal renal and liver function tests, ruling out severe preeclampsia.

Treatment Administered:

1. Antihypertensives:

- Tablet Amlodipine 5 mg once daily was initiated to control postpartum hypertension.

2. Analgesics:

- Jonac suppository cumulative dose of 600 mg was administered for pain relief.

3. Intravenous Fluids:

- Day 1: 2200 mL of Ringer's Lactate
- Day 2: 1500 mL of Normal Saline

4. Antibiotics:

- Injection Ceftriaxone 1 gm twice daily for infection prophylaxis.
- Injection Metronidazole 500 mg thrice daily.

5. Supportive Care:

- Multivitamins and dietary counselling for anaemia correction.

Input and Output Chart:

- Day 1: Fluid intake 2200 mL; urine output 1500mL.
- Day 2: Fluid intake 1500 mL; urine output 1200mL.

Discussion: Postpartum hypertension can potentially be multifactorial. In Mrs. Pooja's case, it might be attributed to:

1. **Drug-Induced Hypertension:** Certain drugs, including excessive fluids or analgesics like NSAIDs (Jonac), may have contributed to transient blood pressure elevation.
2. **Fluid Overload:** The administration of large volumes of IV fluids might have predisposed her to transient fluid overload, contributing to increased blood pressure.
3. **Postpartum Physiological Changes:** The body's adjustment to hemodynamic shifts after delivery could also play a role.

Case 3: Development of Postpartum Hypertension in a Woman with No Prior History of Hypertension

Patient Details:

Mrs. Suganthi, a 29-year-old female (Gravida 2 Para 1), was admitted on 18/01/2024 and underwent an emergency lower segment caesarean section (LSCS) on the same day due to early labour and severe preeclampsia. She delivered twin female babies, with a combined birth weight of approximately 4.2 kg. Her blood group is B-positive, and she was discharged on 30/01/2024.

Obstetric History:

Mrs. Suganthi's **current pregnancy was spontaneous**, and she was regularly booked and immunized. **Anomaly and growth scans showed a twin pregnancy, cephalic presentation, and posterior placenta.** The **amniotic fluid index (AFI) was normal**, and estimated fetal weights were appropriate for gestational age.

She had a **history of one previous LSCS** and no history of recurrent pregnancy loss or assisted reproductive techniques.

Medical History:

- **Hypertension:** No pre-existing hypertension, but BP started fluctuating in the **third trimester.**
- **Diabetes, Thyroid Dysfunction, Epilepsy:** No history.

- **Anaemia:** Mild anaemia was noted during pregnancy, but no blood transfusion was required.
- **MRI Brain Findings:** Features suggestive of **Posterior Reversible Encephalopathy Syndrome (PRES)** were detected postoperatively.

Clinical Course:

Mrs. Suganthi was admitted with complaints of **high blood pressure, severe headache, epigastric pain, and visual disturbances (blurring of vision)**. On admission, BP was **170/110 mmHg**, and urine dipstick showed **3+ proteinuria**, indicating **severe preeclampsia**.

Emergency **LSCS was performed under spinal anaesthesia** due to the risk of maternal and fetal complications. The **immediate intraoperative period was uneventful**, but **postpartum complications** developed by **postoperative day 2 (POD 2)**.

Postpartum Complications:

By POD 2, Mrs. Suganthi developed persistent hypertension (ranging from 160/100 mmHg to 170/110 mmHg), headache, and blurred vision. MRI Brain revealed findings consistent with Posterior Reversible Encephalopathy Syndrome (PRES).

Mild pedal edema was also noted, but renal and liver function tests were within normal limits, ruling out HELLP syndrome or acute kidney injury.

Treatment Administered:

1. Antihypertensives:

- **Tablet Labetalol 100 mg BD** – Titrated as per BP readings.
 - **Tablet Amlodipine 5 mg OD** – Added for sustained BP control.

2. Seizure Prophylaxis:

- **IV Magnesium Sulphate (MgSO₄) infusion** was administered for **24 hours** due to PRES-related neurological symptoms.

3. Analgesics:

- **Tablet Paracetamol 650 mg PRN** for headache.

4. Intravenous Fluids:

- **Day 1:** 2000 mL of Ringer's Lactate
- **Day 2:** 1500 mL of Normal Saline

5. Antibiotics:

- **Injection Ceftriaxone 1 gm BD** for infection prophylaxis.
- **Injection Metronidazole 500 mg TID** to prevent anaerobic infections.

6. Supportive Care:

- **Multivitamins and Iron supplements** for postnatal recovery.
- **Dietary counselling for salt restriction** to manage hypertension.

Input and Output Chart:

Day	Fluid Intake (mL)	Urine Output (mL)
Day 1	2000	1600
Day 2	1500	1400

Discussion:

Postpartum hypertension is a common complication that can have **multifactorial causes**.

In Mrs. Suganthi's case, the potential contributing factors include:

1. Severe Preeclampsia Progressing to Postpartum Hypertension:

- The patient had **severe preeclampsia** during pregnancy, which continued into the postpartum period.
- Elevated BP was **persistent** despite delivery, requiring **multiple antihypertensive agents**.

2. Posterior Reversible Encephalopathy Syndrome (PRES):

- PRES is associated with **severe hypertension and neurological symptoms** such as headache, blurred vision, and altered mental status.

- **BP control and MgSO₄ therapy** were essential in managing her neurological condition.

3. **Fluid Management and Postpartum Adaptation:**

- The **administration of IV fluids** may have contributed to **transient fluid overload**, worsening BP fluctuations.
- **Careful fluid restriction and antihypertensive titration** helped stabilize her condition.

Case 4: Development of Postpartum Hypertension after lower segment caesarean section.

Mrs. V, a 36-year-old primigravida, admitted at 36 weeks + 2 days of gestation was admitted for lower segment caesarean section. The patient had a known case of gestational hypothyroidism and gestational diabetes mellitus on Insulin on regular medication. On admission, patient was awake and oriented. the patient had gestational hypothyroidism and prescribed with tab. Thyronorm 25mcg OD. There was no history of hypertension at home or at emergency room. Her vitals were seem to be normal and closely monitored for maternal and Fetal well-being.

Clinical course:

Her antenatal history was unremarkable, with no history of major illnesses such as, diabetes, and thyroid dysfunction. There was also no history of epilepsy or blood transfusions. During her antenatal care, she was given routine folic acid supplementation, tetanus toxoid injections, and two doses of Inj. Betamethasone to promote fetal lung maturity in anticipation of possible preterm delivery. Physical examination showed no abnormalities, and systemic examinations of her cardiovascular and respiratory systems were normal. The abdominal examination confirmed a cephalic presentation with good fetal movements.

Treatment Given:

1. **Jonac Suppository (Diclofenac):** Cumulative dose of 600 mg post-delivery for pain relief.

2. IV Fluids:

- Day 1: 2000 mL of Ringer's Lactate+ Normal Saline (RL+NS)

Postoperative Course:

- On the fifth day postpartum, the patient developed an elevated blood pressure reading of 160/70 mmHg. This marked increase in blood pressure was managed by initiating the following antihypertensive treatment:

3. **Nifedipine 10 mg STAT**

4. **Amlong A (Amlodipine 5 mg/Losartan 50 mg) BD**

Postpartum Course:

Monitoring and Observations:

Post-delivery, Mrs. V was monitored for vital signs, including blood pressure. A transient rise in BP was noted in postpartum, potentially linked to:

3. **Drug-Induced Effects:** Jonac suppository (diclofenac) is known to cause transient hypertension in certain patients.
4. **Fluid Overload:** The cumulative administration of 2000 mL of IV fluids could have contributed to fluid retention and subsequent BP changes.

Case 5: Development of Postpartum Hypertension after lower segment caesarean section.

Mrs. T, a 36-year-old primigravida, admitted at 37 weeks + 2 days of gestation was admitted for lower segment caesarean section. There was no history of hypertension at home or at emergency room. Her vitals were seem to be normal and closely monitored for maternal and Fetal well-being.

Clinical course:

She had complaints of perceiving Fetal movements and a three-day history of cough, for which a chest X-ray and obstetrician evaluation were advised.

Her antenatal history was unremarkable, with no history of major illnesses such as, diabetes, and thyroid dysfunction. There was also no history of epilepsy or blood transfusions. During her antenatal care, one unit blood transfusion was done and she was given routine folic acid supplementation, tetanus toxoid injections, and two doses of Inj. Betamethasone to promote fetal lung maturity in anticipation of possible preterm delivery. Physical examination showed no abnormalities, and systemic examinations of her cardiovascular and respiratory systems were normal. The abdominal examination confirmed a cephalic presentation with good fetal movements.

Upon admission, her vitals were stable, but considering the risk of preeclampsia, Inj. Magnesium Sulphate ($MgSO_4$) was administered. A loading dose of 4 g was given via slow IV infusion over 20 minutes to prevent and manage potential eclamptic seizures, which are a significant complication of severe preeclampsia. This intervention was followed by close monitoring of her neurological status and vital signs.

Treatment Given:

1. **Inj. Betamethasone:** Two doses administered to enhance fetal lung maturity in anticipation of potential preterm delivery.
2. **Inj. Magnesium Sulphate ($MgSO_4$):** Loading dose of 4 g IV given over 20 minutes to prevent eclamptic seizures in the context of preeclampsia risk.
3. **Jonac Suppository (Diclofenac):** Cumulative dose of 600 mg post-delivery for pain relief.
4. **Zerodol – P:** Cumulative dose of 800 mg post – delivery for pain relief.

IV Fluids:

- Day 1: 2000 mL of Ringer's Lactate+ Normal Saline+ Dextrose normal saline (RL+NS+DNS)
- Day 2: 1500 mL of Dextrose normal saline + Normal Saline (DNS+NS)

Management:

- On the fifth day postpartum, the patient developed an elevated blood pressure reading of 160/70 mmHg. This marked increase in blood pressure was managed by initiating the following antihypertensive treatment:
 1. Inj. Labetalol 100 mg SOS
 2. Nifedipine 10 mg STAT
 3. Amlong A (Amlodipine 5 mg/Losartan 50 mg) BD

Postpartum Course:**Monitoring and Observations:**

Post-delivery, Mrs. V was monitored for vital signs, including blood pressure. A transient rise in BP was noted in postpartum, potentially linked to:

1. **Drug-Induced Effects:** Jonac suppository (diclofenac) is known to cause transient hypertension in certain patients.
2. **Fluid Overload:** The cumulative administration of 3500 mL of IV fluids could have contributed to fluid retention and subsequent BP changes.

DISCUSSION

The cases highlight various presentations of postpartum hypertension in patients with and without prior hypertensive history:

1. Pre-existing Risk Factors:

- Some patients had underlying conditions such as intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR), severe preeclampsia, or gestational diabetes, which may have predisposed them to postpartum hypertensive episodes.
- One patient exhibited signs of posterior reversible encephalopathy syndrome (PRES), a rare but severe neurological manifestation of hypertension.
- Clinical pharmacists played a crucial role in reviewing antenatal medication histories and identifying comorbid risk factors that could potentiate postpartum hypertension. Their insights facilitated tailored pharmacological planning and anticipatory monitoring.

2. Pharmacological Triggers:

- NSAIDs like diclofenac were administered for post-surgical pain relief. These medications are known to cause transient hypertension by inhibiting prostaglandin synthesis, leading to fluid retention and increased vascular resistance.
- Magnesium sulphate (MgSO₄) was used for seizure prophylaxis in preeclampsia cases, but abrupt cessation could have contributed to blood pressure fluctuations.
- Clinical pharmacists actively reviewed postoperative medication charts and identified potential hypertensive agents like NSAIDs. They recommended safer alternatives where necessary and ensured appropriate tapering protocols for magnesium sulphate to minimize abrupt withdrawal effects.

3. Fluid Overload:

- IV fluid administration varied between 2000–4700 mL in different cases. Excessive fluid infusion may lead to transient hypertension due to increased intravascular volume, particularly in patients with compromised endothelial function.
- Pharmacists closely monitored cumulative fluid inputs in collaboration with nursing staff, flagged risks of volume overload, and advised adjustments to fluid therapy based on patient-specific risk profiles and output trends.

4. Postpartum Hemodynamic Shifts:

- The postpartum period involves physiological changes such as blood volume redistribution, hormonal fluctuations, and endothelial recovery, all of which can contribute to transient blood pressure elevations.
- Clinical pharmacists contributed to early detection of these shifts by correlating hemodynamic data with pharmacotherapy changes and guided the team in timely dose modifications or drug discontinuation to avoid exacerbation of hypertension.

5. Management Strategies:

- Antihypertensive medications such as labetalol, amlodipine, nifedipine, and losartan were employed based on patient presentation.
- Close monitoring of input-output balance was essential in managing fluid overload-induced hypertension.
- Supportive care, including dietary counselling and gradual antihypertensive titration,

was implemented to prevent long-term hypertensive complications.

- The clinical pharmacist was instrumental in selecting appropriate antihypertensive agents based on patient-specific factors such as renal function, comorbidities, and breastfeeding status. They also participated in titration strategies, reviewed drug interactions, ensured adherence, and reinforced non-pharmacological measures like salt restriction and hydration management.

CONCLUSION

Postpartum hypertension following LSCS can arise due to a combination of physiological, pharmacological, and procedural factors. Prompt recognition and tailored management are crucial in preventing severe complications. This case series demonstrates that the **clinical pharmacist is a critical contributor** in the early identification and management of such cases. The cases emphasize the importance of:

- Careful selection of analgesics to minimize drug-induced hypertension.
- Judicious fluid management to avoid overload.
- Close postpartum monitoring to detect and address hypertension early.
- Individualized antihypertensive therapy based on the underlying cause and patient response.

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